

VISION EDUCATION : PERSONALISED LEARNING AND ECONOMIC GROWTH

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ABSTRACT:

Personalized learning is an instruction to optimize learning according to the needs of each learner. In 2005, **Dan Buckley** defined two ends of the personalized learning spectrum: "personalization for the learner", and "personalization by the learner". It is a learner-centric, and it has a diverse range of approaches to teaching individual learning needs. Individual unique learning experience to each learner, qualitative education and human capital resources are its main aims. Adaptive technology, project-based learning (PBL), competency-based education are some methods of personalized learning. Adaptive Learning is a technology-led approach which aims to personalise the learning according to the student's factors. According to researcher Eduard Pogorskiy, ICT can be a powerful tool for personalized learning as it allows learners access to research and information, and provides a mechanism for communication. It helps in the development of human capital, productivity, creativity, poverty reduction, encourages entrepreneurship, technological advancements, women empowerment, social development, health awareness, and other areas where economic development can be boosted. Limitations of personalized learning are 'High costs,' 'potential for increased inequality,' 'increased teacher workload,' 'privacy concerns from data collection, leading to student isolation, it will not be successful if there is lack of basic knowledge, and potential for a lack of social interaction and collaboration, lack of facilities etc.

INTRODUCTION :

Human resource development is one of the most important factors of economic growth. Knowledge, ability and skill are the main human resources. These are the human capital for the economic growth. Education has a significant impact on human resource development and a country's economic prosperity by increasing labour productivity and creativity, fostering entrepreneurship, technological improvement, efficient utilisation of resources etc. It improves individual's life quality, health awareness and social stability.

It is most needed to provide qualitative education for the improvement of human knowledge, ability and skill. From person to person, level of knowledge, ability and skill are different. For better development of human resource of a person, Personalised learning is a better method of education.

DEFINITIONS

Personalized learning is an instruction to optimize learning according to the needs of each learner. Learning objectives, methods, and instructional contents vary based on the learner's needs and interest.

Use of the term "personalized learning" dates back to the early 1960s, but there was no widespread definition and components of a personal learning environment.

In 2005, **Dan Buckley** defined two ends of the personalized learning spectrum: "personalization for the learner", in which the teacher tailors the learning to the student, and "personalization by the learner", in which the student develops skills for their own learning.

This spectrum was adopted by the Microsoft's 2006 Practical Guide to Envisioning and Transforming Education.

This type of learning activities are meaningful, relevant to learners and, more effective. it is a learner centric, and it has diverse range of approaches to teaching individual learning needs.

AIMS

1. To create an individual unique learning experience to each learner
2. Understanding the differences in learners
3. To create a opportunity of learning based on their interest
4. To provide qualitative education
5. To improve human capital resources.
6. To announce good citizenship
7. To increase the economic growth under development.

METHODS

some important methods are

1. Adaptive Learning Technology: it is a Software and apps based Technology that adjust content difficulty and pace based on a student's real-time learning performance and provides a adjustable learning experience. It is a technology-led approach which aims to personalise the learning according to the student's factors. In one such system "Yarandi, et al (2012)" modeled a learner profile - based on ability, learning preferences and aspirations - which informed logical sequenced programmes mented to the individual student's needs. In the past, many theorists have given a variety of learning 'styles' that define a student's preferred approach to maximise their learning efficiency. There are many models that suggest learners have a predisposition to a specific style (Kolb, 1984; Honey & Mumford, 1982; Felder & Silverman, 1988). Counter to that, recent research provides evidence that learning 'styles' have little scientific basis. Kirschner (2017) critiques these models to find that a learner has no single optimal learning style, nor that learning styles are requisite to optimal instructional design.
1. Project-Based Learning (PBL): Students explore topics they are passionate about through there own practical experience of working and making learning more engaging and related to their interests
2. Competency Based Learning process : learning progress is based on demonstrating mastery of specific skill and allowing of students to learn at their own pace and become mastered a concept.
3. Personalized Learning Plans: Individualized map planning for each student, marking their unique goals, strengths, and learning strategies to help them reach their full strength..
4. Differentiated Instruction: Teachers frame the curriculum and teaching methods and nature to meet the individual needs of different students groups.
5. Student's nature : if the student willing to learn outside the classroom nature the teacher and the Agencies may aallow them with proper guidance.

TOOLS & ENVIRONMENTS

- Technology, such as learning management systems (LMSs), supports these efforts by providing tools for differentiated instruction, student choice, and progress tracking.
- Learning Management Systems (LMSs) are Platforms like Google Classroom which offer creating of learning groups, assigning differentiated material and facilitating communication.
- Flexible Learning Environments: offering of different zones and equip to support individual work, group collaboration, and various learning activities.
- Formative Assessments : continuous assessments that provide immediate feedback to students and inform instructional adjustments.

According to researcher Eduard Pogorskiy, ICT can be a powerful tool for personalized learning as it allows learners access to research and information, and provides a mechanism for communication, debate, and recording learning achievements. However, personalized learning is not exclusive to digital technologies or environments.

In the rhetoric around 21st Century Skills, personalized learning is often equated with 'customization' with digital personalization used to frame the learning experience as highly efficient.

it can be summarized into three main ways.

First, Building student knowledge is dependent on the current level of knowledge the student has and what kind of support they are provided.

Second, conferring is a model that can provide student support through a structured four-part process.

Third, conferring has been shown to increase student learning in both reading and writing.

To achieve personalized learning many elements of curriculum, assessment, and instructional design must be the in classrooms and instruct the use of software systems.

Alfie Kohn argued in 2015 that while personalized learning may sound like a useful strategy for education, in reality it is a business tactic to increase sales of technology products. Personalized learning promises a strategy to specifically adjust education to the unique needs and skills of individual children.

ROLE OF PERSONALIZED EDUCATION IN THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

1. It helps in the development of human capital, productivity, creativity, poverty reduction, encourages entrepreneurship, technological advancements, women empowerment, social development, health awareness, and other areas where economic development can be boosted.
2. Human capital development : personalized education changes the person into skilled and rational in the critical assessment of the economy.
3. Innovation and technological advancement : enhances and encourages creativity and the ability to innovate new things new ideas and Technology of production process and marketing and also new planning for development.

4. Increased productivity : it increases the skin and deficiency and and capacity of Management. it helps in the quick increase of GDP.
5. Efficient entrepreneurship : it develops confidence and skill of Management which helps in the good combination of factors of production and product maximisation.
6. Increases job opportunities: with good skill and knowledge, it creates more employment opportunities
7. Attainment of Sustainable Development Goals: it helps in sttainment of sustainable development goals, including economic stability.

LIMITATIONS

‘High costs,’ ‘ potential for increased inequality if not implemented equitably,’ increased teacher workload. Additional drawbacks include privacy concerns from data collection, the risk of over-personalization leading to student isolation, it will not be successful if there is lack of basic knowledge, and potential for a lack of social interaction and collaboration, lack of facilities etc.

1. High cost: it requires significant investment in technology, software, and professional development for teachers, which can be a challenge for schools with limited sources.
2. Equity and accessibility: it can worsen existing inequalities if students from disadvantaged backgrounds lack equal access to technology and support.
3. Teacher workload: Teachers face increased demands to manage diverse learning paths,
4. Privacy concerns: The collection and analysis of student data raise privacy and security issues that require careful management.
5. Risk of isolation: There is a risk that focusing too heavily on individualized, self-paced learning can lead to students becoming isolated
6. Potential for uneven progress: The flexibility of personalized learning can cause some students to fall too far behind or get too far ahead.

CONCLUSION

Personalised learning is the one of the best method of learning with targeted aims to achieve vision education and to achieve a drastic economic growth, nowadays many tools and technology are available to support personalized learning. But it is not free from limitations. If the government and organisations take steps to overcome the limitations and implement the personalized learning at different levels levels, it makes easy to achieve vision education.

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